

Survey Questions

1. Are you familiar with the concept of Industry 4.0?
 - yes
 - not sure
 - no

2. What do you most associate the term Industry 4.0 with
 - industry based on automation and robotics
 - new style of enterprise management
 - autonomous manufacturing systems
 - Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT)
 - Big Data
 - artificial intelligence
 - high quality of products
 - digital transformation
 - high demands on employees
 - continuous learning process
 - additive manufacturing
 - I have no opinion
 - other (please specify)

3. Have you participated in seminars/workshops/training/lessons thematically related to Industry 4.0?
 - yes
 - no

- 3a. What was the thematic scope of the seminar/workshop/training/class?
 - basic information about Industry 4.0
 - information on possible applications of Industry 4.0 solutions/tool
 - information on opportunities and threats on the labor market in the conditions of Industry 4.0
 - solving a practical case study in the field of application of Industry 4.0 solutions/tools
 - analysis of practical aspects of implementing Industry 4.0 solutions/tools (both technical and economic)
 - practical contact with the use/handling of Industry 4.0 solutions/tools
 - other (which ones?)

4. Have you undertaken a job/apprenticeship/internship in a company using elements of Industry 4.0?
 - Yes
 - No

4a. How long have you been undertaking a job/apprenticeship/internship in a company using elements of Industry 4.0?

- up to 3 months
- from 3 to 6 months
- from 6 months to 1 year
- from 1 to 2 years
- from 2 to 5 years
- more than 5 years

5. How do you evaluate the phenomenon of Industry 4.0 in the labor market?

- Definitely negative
- Rather negative
- No opinion
- Rather positive
- Definitely positive

6. Do you perceive Industry 4.0 as a threat or an opportunity in the labor market?

- definitely a threat
- rather a threat
- no opinion
- rather an opportunity
- definitely an opportunity

7. Do you have concerns about the future that Industry 4.0 brings in the context of the labor market?

- Yes, I definitely have concerns
- Yes, I have some concerns
- No, I rather do not have concerns
- No, I definitely have no concerns

7a. What aspects would help reduce your concerns about the future that Industry 4.0 brings in the context of the labor market?

- inclusion in the study plans of more classes developing soft skills
- inclusion in the study plans of more classes developing technical skills (e.g. 3D printing, simulation, etc.)
- allowing to spend more time in real companies (more internships)
- creating conditions enabling work in studies (adjustment of the schedule of classes)
- organizing industrial visits
- participation in real projects related to Industry 4.0
- organizing additional (optional) training/workshops on Industry 4.0 solutions
- organization seminars with Industry 4.0 experts
- others (which ones?)

8. Do you see a need in expanding your knowledge of Industry 4.0 in the current reality?

- definitely yes
- rather yes
- no opinion
- rather no
- definitely no

9. To what extent do you think you are prepared for the labor market in an Industry 4.0 environment?

- I am not prepared at all
- I am slightly prepared
- I am averagely prepared
- I am well prepared
- I am very well prepared

Characteristics of respondents

1. Please indicate your age:

- up to 18 years old (inclusive)
- 19 to 22 years old
- 23 to 26 years old
- 27 to 30 years old
- over 30 years old

2. Please indicate your gender:

- Man
- Woman
- I prefer not to answer

3. What year of study are you currently in?

- first year of engineering/bachelor's studies
- second year of engineering/bachelor's studies
- third year of engineering/bachelor's studies
- fourth year of engineering/bachelor's studies
- first year of master's studies
- second year of master's studies

4. What mode of study are you following?

- full-time studies
- part-time studies